

Development of sorghum polishing machine type of three levels of polisher cylinders

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ABSTRACT

The need of polishing the sorghum seed is to reduce the tannin content which is mainly found in the outer skin of the pericarp layers. The high tannin content can reduce the protein digestibility and cause a constipation. Development of a sorghum polishing machine, type of three levels of polisher cylinders, was carried out to improve the previous design of polisher. Previously, farmers re-fed the sorghum seeds into the polisher up to three times. This study developed a machine working in a single feed polishing mechanism. Previously in 2012 and 2016, the Indonesian Center for Agricultural Engineering Research and Development, Serpong developed an abrasive type of sorghum polishing machine with a repetitive feeding (up to 4 times), so the working capacity was low varied between 50-100 kg/hour. This study aims to modify the polisher machine in order to improve the working capacity. The activities consisted of (i) Development a sorghum seed polisher using a main component of abrasive stone; (ii) Development a three levels of polishing mechanism with a single feeding system; (iii) Modification of the screens rotation mechanism working in an opposite direction of the rotation of the abrasive stones. The good quality of the polished seed is shown by the appearance of a full shape and bright color. The performance tests shows that the output capacities were 100-150 kg/hour with tannin content of 0.09% and 3-5% of broken seeds and whiteness of 44.66% with the appearance of whole grain shape and bright color.

Keywords : *sorghum, polisher machine, polisher capacity, sorghum seed quality*

INTRODUCTION

Sorghum seeds (sorghum bicolor) are known as cereal products that contain carbohydrates and high protein and are prospective as substitutes for flour and rice. The difficulty in the use of sorghum seeds to be consumed safely is the removal of the tannin content from the pericarp of the seeds. Pericarp of sorghum seeds blends strongly with the core of the seed (endosperm) which can be consumed safely. The main way to separate the pericarp with the core of the seed is by polishing (abrasive) (Patiwiri, 2006).

The main function of sorghum polishing is not only to obtain white (bright) colour from the seeds but also to reduce tannin levels (phenol

compounds) in the pericarp layer of seeds. Phenol compounds in tannins when bound with prolamin (kafirin) by forming a bond of the tannin protein complex would reduce protein digestibility in the intestine and cause constipation and bloating. The low content of tannin is generally characterized by the appearance of whitish sorghum rice colour (Suarni and Singgih, 2002). The condition of low tannin content is an indicator of the readiness of sorghum seeds to be used for various main ingredients of food and feed. For this reason, it is necessary to use a sorghum machine for efficient and effective use. Some sorghum polishing machines that currently available are not perfect and are still need the improvement in the quantity and quality of products.

Improving the performance and quality of results would be done by modifying existing technologies in the systems and components with more appropriate technology with the impact to improve performance and better quality. The polishing quality parameters include the degree of whiteness, tannin content, the number of damaged sorghum seeds/broken and the yield of silting.

Based on these considerations, it is necessary to modify and develop a repeat silo process to be efficient and effective to be done only once in one machine. In addition, the new design process of sorghum polishing stone and material screw carrier to the polishing parts, so that the flow rate of the material can be increased and the stone polishing capacity can be better, and the repetition of polishing becomes one replication. Uniformity of material that will be fooled can increase the efficiency of polishing.

With the result, the development of Sorghum polishing machine needs to be done to complete and finish of research in the previous year. This study aims to obtain the appropriate sorghum shredding machine by modifying the existing machines.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was carried out during the period of 1 March to 15 December 2017. The location of planning, design, machinery manufacturing, functional testing and verification as well as performance testing is carried out at Engineering Laboratory, BBP Mektan Serpong, whereas laboratory testing is mostly done at the Institute of agricultural Post Harvest research, Bogor. The main engineering materials for the manufacture of sorghum polishing machines include: grinding stone (abrasive stone), diesel engine, blower, iron plate, elbow iron, pulley and belt and other supporting components. While the test material used is sorghum seeds from varieties KD4, Numbu and Kawali. The development and modification of the sorghum polishing machine was carried out with the methods and stages of activities were divided into: preparation

stage, modification and manufacturing stage, testing phase, and reporting phase. Methodology chart is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Engineering process flow chart of sorghum polishing machine

Design of Sorghum Polishing Machine

a. The design of the polishing unit

The theoretical work capacity calculation was done by calculating the screw/auger volume that is capable of carrying sorghum seeds at 850 rpm rotation adjusted to the compression ratio of sorghum seeds entering the polishing chamber and considering the bulk density value.

To increase the polishing capacity, it needs greater contact between the seeds and abrasive stones, but on the other hand the increased contact area would increase the temperature in the polishing chamber and the surface temperature of sorghum seeds. This could reduce the capacity at certain times. Therefore, it is necessary to take the displacement between the initial polishing space and the next space, and during the transfer of the material is cooled on the surface of the sorghum seeds. With this design, it is expected that sorghum seeds and polishing chamber would remain in a constant temperature during processing.

To improve the quality of the results, the polishing was carried out 3 times in parallel to increase the capacity of polishing. Sorghum seeds are accommodated in the hopper and enter the polishing chamber and flow from the first to third polish using the gravity method.

Based on the design, sorghum polishing machine consists of several parts: hopper, polishing system, blower, outlet, transmission system, engine, main frame and stairs. Overall the main parts can be seen in Figures 2, 3 and 4.

1. Hopper

The hopper design is made in the shape of a cone with consideration of the very low cohesion style of sorghum seeds, so that the material can flow easily into the polishing chamber using the gravitational force. The feed process also needs to be regulated by a regulating door to avoid slippage between incoming seeds so that there is no congestion that causes the engine off or the seeds broken.

2. Polishing System

In this section, the polisher consists of the abrasive hollow cone stone and completed with a small iron blower and an auger which serves to channel and push the seeds into the process of polishing. A small blower functions to exhale the air from the outside into the polishing chamber to push dirt (bran) in the abrasive stone hole. In addition, the blower also functions to reduce the level of broken seeds caused by the increase in the temperature of sorghum seeds due to the adhesion and cohesion force. Another part of this machine is the cylindrical screen, which functions to separate the seeds with dirt or bran. In addition, this part also serves as a

medium/intermediary in the process of cohesion force on the erosion of sorghum skin. Abrasive stone consists of 3 units installed parallel to increase the quality of the results and increase the capacity of polishing.

3. Blower

This blower functions to blow out the bran that comes out of the filter cylinder and pushes it out of the machine.

4. Outlet

This section serves as an expenditure polishing seeds equipped with doors that are weighted to provide moments in the process of polishing. Giving this weight burden affects the time of the process of polishing that occurs in it

5. Transmission system

This part serves as a power distributor that comes from the engine. The sorghum seed polishing machine transmission system consists of several components, including:

- 1) Pulley: serves to set the speed of rotation coming from the engine/motor by changing the size of the pulley diameter according to the needs.
- 2) V-belt belt: serves to channel the rotation speed coming from the engine/motor through the pulley. Pulley length is adjusted to the distance between pulleys used. The belt used is type B because it is easily available on the market and adjusted to the type of pulley used
- 3) Bearing: serves as shaft holder. The size of the bearing used is in accordance with the size of the diameter of the axle used so that no slip occurs

6. Engine

The engine uses a 3 phase electric motor 20 kW. Electric motors are chosen as the source of engine because of their practicality in terms of construction and environmental friendliness and low sound. While the weakness is the need for electrical installations.

7. Main Frame

The frame function serves to support the entire system of polishing machine.

8. Stairs

It functions as a tool to help the operator pouring sorghum seeds into the hopper.

Figure 2. Detailed design of sorghum polishing machines

Figure 3. Sorghum polishing machine on side view

Figure 4. Sorghum polishing machine on top and front view

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The overall three-level cylindrical sorghum polishing machine has a dimension of 1350 x 80 x 1350 mm with an electric motor of 20 kW. This machine consists of several main components: polishing unit and supporting components in the form of a frame and engine. This fabricated machinery can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Three-level cylindrical sorghum polishing machine

1. Main component of polishing unit
 - a. Polishing stone design

Abrasive stone is a major component in the design of this prototype machine. The abrasive stone used in this machine is an abrasive stone that has certain shaft dimensions and holes. The abrasive stone for the prototype machine has a stone diameter of 253 mm, a length of 270 mm, a shaft diameter 180 mm and weight 5 kg, produces an optimal polishing capacity with repeated up to 3 times to get sorghum seeds with tannin content that is safe to consume (<0.5%) as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Abrasive stone sketches

Consideration of the length of the abrasive stone arrangement is based on the length of the contact path between the sorghum and the stone surface so that it does not cause excessive heat to sorghum seeds. The occurrence of excessive heat in the seeds due to the friction between the surface of sorghum and abrasive stones results in gelatinization of sorghum seeds (the surface of the seeds will melt). The gelatinization effect will cause dust/bran stick to the sorghum seeds, on the surface of the stone, and can clog concave filter holes which inhibit the output of dust or bran. The thickness of the stone becomes the durability factor of the pressure received from various directions when the process. According to Mwasaro et al., 1988, the roughness of abrasive stones used to excavate high tannin sorghum seeds between 24 mesh (diameter 840 μm) - 46 (diameter 484 μm), while abrasive stones used for polishing machine have mesh 36.

For the process of working the abrasive stone, the center hole of the stone that has a metal wall can be made of a spi hole which serves as a locking stone so that the stone does not move.

Based on the abrasive stone specifications above, the length of the stone required is determined by comparing the length of the path or contact area of the sorghum seeds to the abrasive stone. The wider the contact area will accelerate the process of peeling the skin of the sorghum seeds so that it speeds up the process of polishing. From the calculation results obtained the length of the abrasive stone is needed 240 mm which means it takes abrasive stones with specifications above 1 piece, so that the overall abrasive stone length is 270 mm.

b. Design of Capacity Polishing Unit

The theoretical work capacity calculation is done by calculating the screw/auger volume that is capable of carrying sorghum seeds at 850 rpm rotation and the compression ratio of sorghum seeds entering the polishing room and taking into account the bulk density value. From the results of these calculations obtained a theoretical capacity of 150.5 kg/hour. This value has met the targeted capacity value of 150 kg/hour.

c. Cylindrical screen

Cylindrical screens are made of perforated plates that have a thickness of 1 mm with a profile of oblique rectangular holes (14 x 1.2 mm) and a distance between holes of 2 mm so that the bran is expected to pass through the hole. Perforated holes have a slope of 45° against polishing shaft (Figure 7). The cylindrical screen is designed easier to remove when checking the condition of the stone and other problems that are likely to occur at the polishing process, without the need to open the casing of the output section.

Figure 7. Cylindrical screen in sorghum polishing machine

2. Main Frame and Engine

The main frame design is based on a number of things as parameters, including the dimensions and weight of all components of the polishing unit, the chamber needed by the hopper and consideration of the balance of the polishing unit when operating in relation to the spinning shaft rotation and vibration. For balance, the main frame that has a slim and high shape is designed to blend into the engine seat frame, and the separation unit. To reduce vibration during operation, the lower part of the frame is mounted with bolts (dynabolt).

The power needs are calculated from the power requirements for the polishing unit. Calculation of engine based on the twisting moment that

occurs with the desired engine speed. From the results of the calculation, it was obtained the power for the pilot unit of 20 kW.

Testing Result

From the results of the performance test of sorghum polishing machine, the capacity reached is 100-150 kg/hour. The data of performance test is shown in Table 1 and the polishing seed laboratory test show in Table 2.

Table 1. Performance Testing Result

No.	Variety	Shaft polishing speed (rpm)		Blower speed (rpm)		Seed mass (kg)		Polshing time (min)	Capacity (kg/hr)
		TB	DB	TB	DB	in	out		
1	Numbu	763	735	3105	3050	150	120	60	150
2	KD-4	741	733	3100	3047	100	60	60	100

Table 2. The quality of sorghum seeds in one polishing replication

No.	Parameter	Result	Unit
1.	Capacity	100-150	kg/hr
2.	Tannin content	0.09	%
3.	Whiteness	46.66 (bright)	%
4.	Whole seed	91.6-92.2	%
5.	Broken seed	3.52-6.0	%
6.	Rendemen	60-75	%

Based on the results of chemical and physical laboratory tests, the sorghum polishing machine is able to reduce the tannin content in accordance with the consumption needs and broken beans 3-6% with maximum discharge 1 time.

CONCLUSIONS

The third level sorghum polishing machine consists of main parts: hopper, polishing system, blower, outlet, transmission system, engine, main frame and stairs. Overall, this machine has been able to polish sorghum seeds with 1 (one) replication time in one machine so that the capacity of 100-150

kg/hour with an overall seed quality of 91.6% - 92,2 % and broken seeds around 3-6% and whiteness values 46.66% (bright) with an average tannin level of 0.09%

REFERENCES

- Patiwiri, A.W. 2006. Teknologi Penggilingan Padi. Jakarta. PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama *dalam* Wiwit Amrinola. 2010. Kajian Pembuatan Nasi Sorgum (*Sorghum Bicolor L*) Instan Rendah Tanin. Tesis. Sekolah Pascasarjana, Institut Pertanian Bogor.
- Suarni dan S. Singgih. 2002. Karakteristik Sifat Fisik dan Komposisi Kimia Beberapa Varietas/Galur Biji Sorgum. *Jurnal Stigma X* (2): 127-130.
- Mwasaru, M. A., Reichert, R. D., & Mukuru, S. Z. 1988. Factors affecting the abrasive dehulling efficiency of high-tannin sorghum. *Cereal Chemistry*, 65(3), 171-174.